

DEVELOPING SDN-BASED INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM MODEL:A METHODOLOGICAL REVIEW

Umar Baba Umar^{*1}, Abbas Yahya Yakub^{*2},

^{*1}Student, Library and Information Technology , Minna,Niger State, Nigeria

^{*2}Student, Information Technology, ATBU, Bauchi,Bauchi State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Cyber-attacks are becoming more sophisticated and thereby presenting increasing challenges in accurately detecting intrusions. Failure to prevent the intrusions could degrade the credibility of security services, e.g. data confidentiality, integrity, and availability (Gondal et al, 2019). The overall perception is that SDN capabilities will ultimately result in improved security. However, in its raw form, SDN could potentially make networks more vulnerable to attacks and harder to protect (Buyya, 2018). Intrusion detection system “IDS” are considered as the one of the best solutions for network security (Abbas et al, 2020). The aim of study is to review different articles on intrusion detection systems. After reviewing 50 articles, we discovered that many of the articles have employed the use of KDD CUP 99 dataset which is an outdated dataset. We also made recommendations on future investigations.

Keywords: Intrusion Detection, system, Design, Implementation,

I. INTRODUCTION

The architecture of the conventional networking has been developed for almost three decades and now, it is becoming a very complex system especially in this era of hyper-connected world. This highly decentralized network, was built from combinations of large hardware network devices such as the router, switches, and so many other types of middleboxes (Des, Tang, Mnamdi, Zaidi, & Ghogho, 2019). It requires network administrators to configure each of the network devices separately through a low-level vendor-specific commands. Making configuration and reconfiguration in response to changes in a heterogeneous network environment very tedious and virtually impossible. In order to resolve this short coming, demands a more flexible framework (Buyya, Kaafar, & Shaghghi, 2018).

Foresta et al.'s 2018 study (as cited in Abbas, Reza, Dehghantanha, & Muhammed, 2020), software defined networking (SDN) was introduced in order to resolve the limitations of the conventional networking due to unavoidably daily increase in the numbers of network users. This will create flexibility in network management, efficient controlling of traffics, high programmability, adaptability and automation. According to Jin, Keeping, Yang, & Wenduam (2020), based on research conducted on experiences of 165 senior IT leaders from large organizations, it was found that around 15% of the organizations have already implemented SDN and up to 57% of respondents expect to deploy SDN in near future. This confirmed that the future of networking, lies in SDN.

Despite the flexibility offered by SDN, the architecture showcases so many network security challenges that must be addressed in order to strengthen SDN network security structures (Des et al., 2019).

One of the perceptions of SDN benefits is that, its capabilities will improve the network security however, in its raw form, SDN could make the networks more vulnerable to attacks and harder to protect (Buyya et al., 2018). Intrusion detection system “IDS” are considered as one of the best solutions for network security (Abbas et al, 2020). Although, performances of IDS's detection techniques, depends on the quality of the training datasets unfortunately, most published studies have employed non compactable and outdated datasets in implementing SDN-based IDS. As a result, conclusions from these studies could be unreliable and misleading (Elsayed, Le-Khac, & Jurcut, 2020). Therefore, in Designing IDS to meet today's ICT security demand, updated datasets

and appropriate, and efficient algorithm must be used in order to attain detection accuracy for new and existing cyber-attacks (Abbas et al, 2020).

II. RELATED WORK

In order to improve the security of a software defined networking, this study reviewed literatures based on the following contexts: conceptual reviews, reviews of related work, empirical reviews and theoretical reviews. This is to give a better understanding of the current state art in software defined network security by exploring methodologies used by past researchers and developers, detect weaknesses in the already proposed systems and ways to improve these weaknesses.

2.2 Conceptual Reviews

This research, is conceptualized based on software defined networking (SDN), network attacks, intrusion detection system (IDS), datasets and artificial intelligence.

2.2.1 Software defined networking

The SDN technology was mainly introduced to revolutionize network design and operation by enabling the programming of the various networking services, and centralized the network management by abstracting the control plane from the data forwarding function Jin et al., (2020).

The major concept of SDN is the decoupling of the control plane and the data plane, where the controller creates the flow tables and distributes them to the switches, which are only responsible for forwarding the data packets (Abbas et al, 2020). The key benefits of SDN is the ability to add services to the network as applications that run within the controller without adding any devices or modifying the network's topology. Also, it provides a centralized networking paradigm which can be remotely controlled via API (Hoang, 2015).

Typical SDN architecture consists of application plane, control plane and data plane. SDN depends on both northbound Interface and southbound Interface to communicate amongst the planes. The Northbound Interface (NBI) is used for communication among the application and the control layer, whereas the south bound interface (SBI) allows the control layer to communicate with the data layer and vice a versa (Hande & Muddana, 2020).

Figure 1

SDN Architecture

Note. By Jena, S. (2020).

2.2.2 Network attacks

Attacks refer to any techniques employed by hackers and attackers in order to compromise or bridge the security of network. Attacks on network are broadly categorized into four

(Atkinson, Bellekens, Hamilton, Hodo, & Tachtatzis, 2017). DoS attacks is a class of attacks that direct unwanted traffics to a particular network in order to deny legitimate users access to the services render by such network. This include Smurf, TCP SYN flooding, teardrop etc., probe attack refers to attacks that scans through networks in order to collect information about the devices. Typical of probe attacks include the following; port sweep scan ports to determine which service is running on the host, ping sweep launches some range of ip addresses that correspond to the live hosts, User to Root (U2R) class of attacks try to gain superuser privileges through usual user account e.g. buffer overflow, and the last class of network attack is Remote to Local (R2L) which broadcast packets to remote system through the network in order to gain access (Hande & Muddana, 2020).

2.2.3 Intrusion detection system (IDS)

Intrusion detection system (IDS) is incorporated into a network in order to identify threats by monitoring packets transmitted over the network or the usage of computer resources. IDS detect anomalous and malicious activities from both in and outside intruder. It can be classified as Host-based when it runs on a network host, or network-based when it monitors network (Alhadad, Chilamkurti, Sultana, & Peng, 2019). Based on detection techniques, IDS can be divided into signature-based detection, where it inspects and detect features that correspond to known malicious packets or system usage pattern, or anomaly-based detection, where it looks for patterns that deviate from normal behavior (Abbas et al., 2020). The signature-based IDS identify malicious attacks with less false rate but cannot detect zero-day attacks hence demanding the signatures to updated on a constant basis. The aim of anomaly-based IDS is to detect unknown malicious activities (Randy, & Wang, 2017).

2.2.4 Dataset

IDS datasets are developed by collecting traces of real network traffics and computer resources usage. These datasets were used for benchmarking the performances of intrusion detection system. DARPA is the first dataset for IDS generated in 1998 by the MIT Lincoln Laboratory under the DARPA funded project. DARPA dataset do not represent actual network traffic, it is characterized with attack data irregularities and it provide no false-positive instances (Lohiya & Thakkar, 2019).

KDD CUP 99 and NSL-KDD datasets are Descendants of DARPA dataset and they top the list of most used dataset. In 1999, after refining and reprocessing the DARPA tcpdump files by the university of California, the KDD CUP 99 was developed which was characterized with high degree of data redundancy which was later remove to arrive at NSL-KDD. However, NSL-KDD datasets contain a limited number of attacks type Elsayed et al., (2020).

CICIDS 2017 dataset is considered as one of the most recent datasets by many researchers. It is revolutionized version of ISCX2012 dataset published in 2012. The major difference between CICIDS 2017 and its ancestor, is that CICIDS contain 80 flow-based features in contrast to 20 packet features of its ancestor. More also, CICIDS 2017 contain https beta profile. Backlashes of CICIDS 2017 include, over 280000 missing class label and over 200 missing information instances Elsayed et al., (2020).

CSE-CIC-IDS2018 was generated as a collaborative project between the Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity (CIC) and Communication Security Establishment (CSE) using Amazon web services (AWS) computing platform. Systematic approach was used to generate the dataset base on profile notions where, B-profiles generate normal traffic and M-profiles generate attack scenarios. It contains same attacks scenarios as in CICIDS 2017 and as such, inherit same setbacks of CICIDS 2017 in addition to the use synthetic traffic Elsayed et al., (2020).

2.2.5 Artificial intelligence

The enhancement of large volumes of data, requirement for the development of large computational power and storage has made AI popular (Hande & Muddana, 2020). Artificial intelligence is one of the latest technologies that allowed the computers (machine), to mimic behavior of the human. This concept plays an important role in detecting, malicious features in intrusion detection system, and widely used in developing intrusion system (Jacob & Kanimozhi, 2019).

Machine learning and deep learning, remained the most popular fields of artificial intelligence in intrusion detection system. The machine learning field uses statistical methods informs of algorithms to examined data, learn from the data and make intelligent decisions supporting what it learns. Deep learning is a talented method in detection system that structured algorithm into layers from which it learned and make intelligent decision on its own and automatically find correlations in data (Hande & Muddana, 2020).

Ensemble learning is a potent technique to improve the performance of machine learning model. Its goal is to better the predictions accuracy by combining predictions from multiple machine learning model (such as classifiers) to provide solution to a particular problem (Paul, 2018). There are three major methods of ensemble learning. These are the bagging, the stacking and the boosting (Brownlee, 2021a).

Bagging also known as bootstrap aggregation method of ensemble learning, fit many decision trees on more than one samples of same dataset and compute average of the predictions from these decision trees to arrive at the final prediction (Brownlee, 2021b)

Boosting is a sequential learning method in which the algorithm works by training a model with whole of the training dataset, then subsequent models are constructed by fitting the errors value of the initial model. It always gives higher weight to those observations with poor estimate in the previous model. Typical of boosting are the extreme gradient boosting (XGBoosting), gradient boosting machine (GBM) and adaptive boosting (ADABOOST) (Paul, 2018).

Voting based ensemble learning (Stacking) is of the most straight forward ensemble learning method which combine predictions from multiple model. This method starts by creating more than one separate models with the same dataset and use the stacking learning method is used to wrap the previous models, and aggregate predictions of the previous model (Paul, 2018).

2.3 Empirical Review

this section provides reviews on SDN security issues, IDS detections techniques and ensemble learning in IDS.

2.3.1 SDN security

Currently, SDN is widely implemented by many data center's network environment however, just like most emerging technology, SDN also comes with security vulnerabilities and threat (Elsayed et al., 2020). SDN is never immune to the popular network attacks, as if that is not enough, SDN is even more sensitive to network attacks than the traditional network. Attacks in traditional network, is only regulated to the portion of the network with same vendor without bringing down the entire network but this is not the case with SDN. A compromised switches or end-users can disrupt the SDN controller, resulting into damage for the entire network (Abbas et al., 2020). SDN poses certain features which increases its security vulnerability. These features include: forwarding device management protocol, a centralized controller, open programmable interfaces, third-party network services and virtualized logical networks (Buyya et al., 2018).

2.3.2 IDS detection techniques

Intrusion detection system majorly rely on two type of detection techniques in order to identifies threat on a network or on a host computer. These techniques are; signature-based and anomaly-based (Hande & Muddana, 2020).

2.3.2.1 Signature-based intrusion detection system

Signature-based intrusion detection systems (SIDS) are based on pattern matching techniques to find a known attack. these are also known as Knowledge-based Detection or Misuse Detection (Gondal, Khraisat, & Vamplew, 2018). In SIDS, matching methods are used to find a previous intrusion. In other words, when an intrusion signature matches with the signature of a previous intrusion that already exists in the signature database, an alarm signal is triggered. For SIDS, host's logs are inspected to find sequences of commands or actions which have previously been identified as malware. SIDS have also been labelled in the literature as Knowledge-Based Detection or Misuse Detection (Modi et al., 2013).

SIDS usually gives an excellent detection accuracy for previously known intrusions (Gondal, et al., 2019). However, SIDS has difficulty in detecting zero-day attacks for the reason that no matching signature exists in the database until the signature of the new attack

is extracted and stored.

2.3.2.2 Anomaly-based intrusion detection system (AIDS)

AIDS has drawn interest from a lot of scholars due to its capacity to overcome the limitation of SIDS. In AIDS, a normal model of the behavior of a computer system is created using machine learning, statistical-based or knowledge-based methods. Any significant deviation between the observed behavior and the model is regarded as an anomaly, which can be interpreted as an intrusion. The assumption for this group of techniques is that malicious behavior differs from typical user behavior. The behaviors of abnormal users which are dissimilar to standard behaviors are classified as intrusions. Development of AIDS comprises two phases: the training phase and the testing phase. In the training phase, the normal traffic profile is used to learn a model of normal behavior, and then in the testing phase, a new data set is used to establish the system's capacity to generalize to previously unseen intrusions. The main advantage of AIDS is the ability to identify

zero-day attacks due to the fact that recognizing the abnormal user activity does not rely on a signature database (Alazab, Hobbs, Abawaj, & Alhazam, 2012). AIDS triggers a danger signal when the examined behavior differs from the usual behavior.

2.3.3 Ensemble leaning in IDS

Ensemble learning is a machine learning technique that seeks better predictions accuracy by combining predictions from multiple models (Brownlee, 2021).

Foo, Jeffrey, Lahza, Pham, & Suriadi (2018), proposed IDS that used feature selection and ensemble model. The ensemble models were built based on bagging and boosting techniques using tree-based algorithm as the based classifier. Cheng, Dai, Jiang, & Zhou (2020), proposed a novel detection framework based on feature selection and ensemble learning techniques. The ensemble classifier is based on C4.5, RF and Forest PCA with the AOP rule introduced to construct the classification model. Abbas et al., (2020), implemented SDN-based IDS based on the voting system of the ensemble learning. The voting system comprises of several machine learning algorithm. The SVM is chosen to separate the dataset geometrically, decision tree, random forest and XGBoost are used to obtain better predictions depending on the probabilistic distribution of the features and finally, deep neural is used for finding patterns in the datasets.

2.4 Review of related research Models/Architectures/Frameworks

Des et al., (2019) proposed a deep learning based SDN'IDS using a gated recurrent unit recurrent neural network (GRU-RNN). The proposed model was trained and tested using NSL-KDD and CICIDS2017 datasets. The model recorded 89 and 99% accuracy respectively. However, the proposed framework increases the controller overhead and also benchmarked the performances of their model on NSL-KDD dataset which is considered outdated and unfit for an SDN-based IDS according to Elsayed et al., (2020), and the CICIDS dataset, even though generated in 2017, which is a fairly recent brand, unfortunately, was not generated from an SDN network but from the conventional network.

Alenazi & Alzahrani (2020), develop an SDN-based IDS machine learning model. The model was built using the boosting ensemble learning (XGBoost) techniques and other classical ML algorithms such as decision tree, random forest in order to improve on the detection accuracy. The study uses NSL-KDD as the dataset for benchmarking and features as a counter (FaaC) data preprocessing method to process the raw data. The experimental result recorded 95% accuracy however, the study did not consider the impact of network dataset on the performance of model and more also, underwent some unnecessary processes in building the model and also, like Des et al., (2019), benchmarked the performances of the model on NSK-KDD dataset. Abbas et al., (2020), proposed a machine learning- based IDS for SDN using the voting system of ensemble learning. The system directly receives features from the SDN which solve issue of increased controller overhead inherent Des et al., (2019). The experimental result recorded 79% of accuracy and 0.03% reduction in false positive rate. Unfortunately, like Alenazi & Alzahrani (2020), this study also utilized NSL-KDD for benchmarking. NSL-KDD dataset is unfit and outdated for an SDN-based IDS Elsayed et al., (2020).

2.4 Theoretical Reviews

This study is underpinned to the system and attack model by (Crescenzo, Ghosh, & Talpade, 2005). Where a network is called autonomous system (AS), which may have many points of entry, for network traffic refer to as border gateways (BG) of the network. BG is generated by external users, without loss of generality, each user can send to each BG. The model considers network traffic as a sequence of atomic packets, where each packet can be abstracted as a tuple $p = (sid, time, poe, pl)$, where sid is the identity of the sender, time is the time stamp of action, poe is the point of entry and pl stand for payload. At any time, action in a AS system, can be describe as a stream of packets entering AS through BG. Attack can be any sequence of c (packets), for some $c \geq 1$, that successfully alters the state of machines in AS in order to achieve a specific (malicious) goal.

2.5 Summary of Research Gaps

Major gaps discovered throughout the reviews done for this study, are summarized in the table below. It shows the author/s involved, the year of publications, methodologies used, dataset used, result and the limitations of their approaches.solutions

III. RESEAERCH METHODOLOGY

According to EBSCO (2017) research instrument are measurable tools eg (observation. interview, record inspection design to obtain data on the topic under study. The data use for this research Is gotten from secondary sources by browsing through articles on the internet.

3.3 Method of data presentation

In other to present data about the current system such as how it works and the problem identified with it, the Structured System Analysis and Design(SSAD)approach is used. Structured system analysis and design method(SSADM) is a system approach to the analysis and design of in

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Major gaps discovered throughout the reviews done for this study, are summarized in the table below. It shows the author/s involved, the year of publications, methodologies used, dataset used, result and the limitations of their approaches.

Table 1

Summary of research gaps

Author/s	Year	Methodologies	Dataset used	Results	Limitations
Des et al.,	2019	Deep learning	NSL-KDD	89% accuracy	Outdated and unfit
			and	from	dataset used and
			CICIDS2017	NSL-KDD	increased in
				and 99% controller overhead	

				accuracy from (Latency)	
				CICIDS2017	
Alenazi & Alzahrani	2020	Machine learning (Ensemble learning)	NSL-KDD	95% accuracy	Unfit and outdated dataset used and unnecessary procedures adopted
Abbas et al.,	2020	Machine learning (Ensemble learning)	NSL-KDD and KDDCup 99	79% accuracy	Do not consider effect of network dataset on performance of IDS

V. CONCLUSION

5.1 Summary

After reviewing 50 articles, we discovered that many of the articles have employed the use of KDD CUP 99 dataset which is an outdated dataset. The performance of these detection techniques relies on the quality of the training dataset (Elsayed, 2020). NSL-KDD is a refined version of KDD CUP 99 dataset and consists of a limited number of attack types (Lohiya & Thakkar, 2019). Although many studies have employed KDD'99 and NSL-KDD in the domain of intrusion detection, both datasets are not realistic to represent the current network traffic since they were generated two decades ago and cannot reflect the current attack trends (Elsayed et al, 2020). Deviation from using the right dataset, will force the IDS to perform beyond optimal level as witnessed in Abbas et al (2020).

5.3 Recommendations

In view of the details of the conclusion of this research and summary discussed above, this research result finds out that :

1. Deviation from using the right dataset, will force the IDS to perform beyond optimal level as witnessed in Abbas et al (2020).
2. The use of inSDN dataset will improve the accuracy of Intrusion detection systems.

III. REFERENCES

- [1] Abbas, Y., Reza, P., Dehghantaha, A., & Muhammed, K. (2020). A kangaroo-based intrusion detection on software defined networks. *Computer Networks*, 184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2020.107688>
- [2] Alazab, A., Hobbs, Abawajy, M., & Alhhazam, M. (2012). Using feature selection for intrusion detection system. *International Symposium on Communications and Information Technologies*, 2012, 296-301. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCIT.2012.6380910>
- [3] Alenazi, M., & Alzahrani, A. (2021). Designing a network intrusion detection system based on machine learning for software defined networks. *Future Internet*, 13(5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/fil305011>
- [4] Alhadad, R., Chilamkurti, N., Sultana, N., & Peng, W. (2019). Survey on SDN based network intrusion detection system using machine learning approaches. *Peer-to-Peer Networking and application*, 12(2), 493-501. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12083-017-0630-0>
- [5] Atkinson, R., Bellekens, X., Hamilton, A., Hodo, E., & Tachtatzis, C. (2017). Shallow and deep networks intrusion detection system: a taxonomy and survey. *Procedia Computer Science*, 171, 644-653. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2020.04.070>
- [6] Brownlee, J. (2021). Make better predictions with bagging, boosting and stacking. <https://machinelearningmastery.com/ensemble-learning-algorithms-with-python/>
- [7] Brownlee, J. (2021, April 27). A gentle introduction to ensemble learning algorithm. [Machinelearningmastery.com/tour-of-ensemble-learning-algorithm/](https://machinelearningmastery.com/tour-of-ensemble-learning-algorithm/)
- [8] Buyya, R., Kaafar, A. M., & Shaghghi, A. (2018). Software-defined network (SDN) data plane security: issue, solutions and future directions. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324167015>
- [9] Cheng, G., Dai, M., Jiang, S., & Zhou, Y. (2020). Building an efficient intrusion detection system based on features selection and ensemble classifier. *Computer Network*, 174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2020.107247>
- [10] Crescenzo, D. G., Ghosh, A., & Talpade, R. (2005). Towards a theory of intrusion detection. *European Symposium on Research in Computer Security*, 3679, 267-286. https://doi:10.1007/115558827_16
- [11] Des, M., Tang, T., Mnamdi, L., Zaidi, R., & Ghogho, M. (2019). Intrusion Detection in SDN-Based Networks: Deep recurrent neural network pproach. *Advanced sciences and technologies for security*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-13057-2_8
- [12] Elsayed, S., Le-Khac, N., & Jurcut, D. (2020). InSDN: A Novel SDN Intrusion Dataset. *IEEEAccess*, 8, 165263-165284. <https://doi-0.1109/ACCESS.2020.3022633>
- [13] Foo, E., Jeffrey, H., Lahza, M. F.H., Pham, T. N., & Suriadi, S. (2018). Improving performance of intrusion detection system using ensemble methods and feature selection. *Proceedings of Australasian Computer Science Week Multiconference*, 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3167918.3167951>
- [14] Gondal, I., Khraisat, A., & Vamplew, P. (2018). An anomaly intrusion detection system using C5 decision tree classifier. *Pacific-Asia Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 11154, 149-155. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-04503-6_14
- [15] Hande, Y., & Muddana, A. (2020). A survey on intrusion detection system for software defined networks (SDN). *International Journal of Business Data Communications and Networking*, 16 (1) 1-17. <https://doi:10.4018/978-1-7998-7705-9.ch03>
- [16] Hoang, D. (2015). Software defined networking shaping up for the next disruptive step. *Australian journal of telecommunication and digital economy*, 3. <https://telsoc.org/ajde-v3-n4/a28>
- [17] Jacob, T. & Kanimozhi, V. (2019). Artificial intelligence-based network intrusion detection with hyper-parameter optimization tuning on the realistic cyber dataset CSE-CIC-IDS2018 using cloud computing. *ICT Express*, 5 (3), 211-214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icte.2019.03.003>
- [18] Jena, S. (2020). Diffrence between software defined network and traditional network. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/diffrence-between-software-defined-network-and-traditional-network>
- [19] Jin, L., Keeping, Y., Yang, X., & Wenduam, L. (2020). Challenge-based Collaborative Intrusion Detection in Software Defined Networking. *Digital Communications and Networks*, 7(2), 257-263.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dcan.2020.09.003>

- [20] Lohiya, R., & Thakkar, A. (2019). A review of the advancement in intrusion detection datasets. *Procedia Computer Science*, 167, 636-645. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2020.03.330>
- [21] Modi, C., Patel, D., Borisaniya, B., Patel, H., Patel, A., Rajarajan, M. (2013). A survey of intrusion detection techniques in cloud. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 36(1), 42-57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2012.05.003>
- [22] Paul, S. (2018, September 6). Ensemble learning in python. www.datacamp.com/tutorials/ensemble-learning-python
- [23] Randy, J. & Wang, L. (2017). Big data analytics for network intrusion detection: A Survey, *International Journal of Networks and communications*, 7(1), 24-31. <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.ijnc.20170701.03>
- [24]